

Hybrid approach to eye blinking detection for low-resource embedded systems

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Abstract — This article presents a hybrid approach for real-time eye blink detection, specifically designed for low-resource embedded devices. The proposed eye blink detection system combines the fast and inexpensive Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) geometric method with a lightweight convolutional neural network based on the MobileNetV2 architecture, used only in cases of ambiguity. This conditional strategy optimises the computational load while improving the robustness and accuracy of the system. Experiments have shown an overall accuracy of 95%, with an average processing time of 19 ms per image. The model has been successfully deployed on a web application via TensorFlow.js, proving its portability and adaptability to embedded environments. This ingenious, fast and easy-to-implement technique paves the way for practical applications in the fields of road safety, digital health and accessibility.

Keywords — Eye blinking, embedded systems, EAR, MobileNetV2, real-time detection

I. INTRODUCTION

In an increasingly connected world, intelligent embedded systems play a central role in the development of interactive and autonomous technologies. These devices, often integrated into resource-constrained environments, must meet growing demands in terms of responsiveness, energy consumption and robustness [1], [2]. Among the most promising biometric signals, blinking is an essential indicator used in a wide variety of applications such as detecting drowsiness [3] at the wheel, unlocking phones, contactless human-machine interfaces [4], and passive medical monitoring [3], [4].

However, integrating reliable blink detection into embedded systems remains a challenge. Geometric methods such as Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) [1] [5] used in eye blink detection are fast and inexpensive to compute, but their reliability decreases significantly in the presence of brightness variations, complex viewing angles or occlusions [6]. EAR is based on an efficient and simple calculation based on the ratio of distances

between ocular landmarks [1]. Conversely, convolutional neural network (CNN) approaches, such as ResNet [7] or VGG16, offer high accuracy, but at the cost of excessive resource consumption [8], [9].

These constraints make it difficult to deploy them on low- capacity embedded platforms. In [10], R. Ibrahim et al. (2021) proposed an eye-blinking system for embedded systems by combining EAR and machine learning through a Haar cascade classification algorithm. In this article, the eyes are first detected using a facial landmark detection algorithm based on images obtained from a Raspberry Pi 3 camera. For Hong J. et al. [11], eye blink detection is essential in the automated assessment of an individual's physical and mental state. The authors emphasise the need to use high-quality images, while taking capture angles into account. They propose a new architecture, DE-ViViT (Dual Embedding Video Vision Transformer), based on a video transformer and two encoding strategies : tubelet embedding captures macroscopic changes in the video sequence using 3D convolutions, and residual embedding captures micro- variations between key images. In [12], the authors propose an eye blink detection system based on EAR. However, according to Safarov et al. (2023), detection based solely on EAR, although fast, lacks robustness in the face of visual disturbances such as lighting variations or partial occlusions such as wearing glasses. The work in [13] and [14] argues that machine learning is an interesting alternative in terms of effectiveness in the face of these disturbances. Thus, DE LA CRUZ et al. (2022) propose Eye-LRCN (Long-Term Recurrent Convolutional Network), a hybrid architecture that combines a Siamese network (Siamese CNN) and a bidirectional LSTM for more robust blink detection. However, the feature extractor (the Siamese network) accounts for 95% of the

inference time, resulting in a very high computational cost that limits its real-time deployment on devices with limited resources. DE LIMA MEDEIROS et al. (2022) propose a system based on a computer vision pipeline. They first detect the face using an SSD (Single Shot Multibox Detector) model, then extract the eye regions and finally evaluate their quality using a CNN. According to the authors, this approach is effective, inexpensive and suitable for real-time use. Nevertheless, its performance can be affected by lighting variations and sudden movements. In [15], Xiong et al. (2025) propose a systematic review following the PRISMA standard of forty-eight (48) articles published between 2017 and 2024 devoted to the use of deep learning for eye blink detection. The authors highlight the excellent performance of Deep learning in visual feature extraction, but also point out that these models are often too heavy for deployment on embedded systems. They recommend the use of lighter CNN models and the development of models optimised for inference on edge and mobile devices.

Thus, some authors have explored hybrid approaches, combining the advantages of geometric methods and deep learning methods [16], [17] to design systems capable of combining speed of execution, accuracy, and adaptability to real-world and embedded environments.

In this article, we propose an original hybrid solution combining the EAR geometric method with an optimised MobileNetV2 CNN [9], with the aim of detecting eye blinks efficiently, quickly and in real time, while respecting the hardware constraints of embedded devices. The system is based on rapid initial detection by EAR, followed by validation by CNN only in cases of ambiguity, which reduces false positives without unnecessarily slowing down processing.

The main contributions of this work are as follows :

- The design of a real-time detection pipeline based on adaptive EAR–CNN integration ;
- A comprehensive experimental evaluation under various conditions (standard lighting, low light, occlusions) ;

Multi-platform deployment via TensorFlow.js conversion [18] and hosting on AWS S3, demonstrating the feasibility of browser-based access without installation.

The rest of this article is organised as follows : Section II describes the hardware, software

libraries used, and the proposed methodology. Section III presents the experimental results and system performance. Section IV discusses the advantages, limitations, and prospects for improvement. Section V presents the deployment. Finally, Section VI concludes the article by summarising the contributions and opening up avenues for future research.

II. HARDWARE, SOFTWARE AND METHODS

A. Hardware

The experiments were conducted on an HP EliteBook 840 G5 laptop (Fig. 1), chosen for its ability to support computer vision processing and lightweight neural network training. This PC is equipped with an Intel® Core™ i7- 8650U processor (8th generation, 4 cores, base frequency of 1.90 GHz up to 4.20 GHz in Turbo mode), 24 GB of DDR4 RAM and a 512 GB NVMe™ SSD, ensuring high read/write speeds. The graphics system is based on an Intel® UHD Graphics 620 card, which is sufficient for real-time image processing. The whole system runs on Windows

10 Pro 64-bit, providing a stable environment for development and deployment.

For video capture, we used the device's built-in HD webcam, which allows for smooth frame acquisition in a variety of lighting conditions. Although basic, this camera offers sufficient resolution and frame rate to simulate the conditions of use of a standard embedded system.

Fig. 1 an HP EliteBook 840 G5 laptop

B. Software and libraries

Development was carried out using the Visual Studio Code [19] (VS Code) environment, a modern, lightweight and extensible code editor particularly suited to Python projects. It enabled efficient management of scripts, virtual

environments and tests, thanks to the integration of specific machine learning extensions.

The programming language used is Python 3 [20] version 8.10, recognised for its simplicity, its widespread adoption in the scientific community and its compatibility with image. The main libraries used are listed below :

- OpenCV 4.5.3: for capturing, processing and analysing images/videos [1].
- MediaPipe [2] 0.8.6: for detecting facial landmarks (particularly key points around the eyes) [2].
- NumPy [18] 1.21.2: for numerical vector operations.
- SciPy 1.7.1: used here to calculate Euclidean distances between facial points.
- TensorFlow [21] 2.6.0: for creating, training and inferring the MobileNetV2 [9] [3] neural network model.
- Matplotlib 3.4.3: for visualising results (accuracy curves, loss, etc.).

All of these tools were selected for their compatibility with embedded environments and their ability to operate efficiently in real time.

C. Methodology

The first step in our pipeline is to quickly detect eye blinks using a geometric approach based on the Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) [1]. This method, introduced by Soukupová and Čech (2016), is based on analysing the distances between six key points (Fig. 2) located around each eye. These points are automatically extracted using the MediaPipe library [2], which provides 468 facial landmarks in real time, including a dozen dedicated to the eye region.

Fig. 2 Open eye and closed eye [1]

Once the points have been detected, the EAR is calculated using the following formula :

$$EAR = \frac{\|P_2 - P_6\| + \|P_3 - P_5\|}{2 \times \|P_1 - P_4\|}$$

where P_1, P_2, P_3, P_4, P_5 et P_6 represent coordinates of key points placed on the upper and lower eyelids, as well as on the inner and outer corners of the eye. The numerator measures the vertical aperture, while the denominator measures the horizontal width of the eye. In our implementation, an empirical threshold of 0.24 is used to differentiate between an open eye and a closed eye. If the EAR value falls below this threshold for several consecutive frames, a blink is detected. This choice is based on empirical observations from our annotated database.

One of the main advantages of this method is its computational simplicity. The EAR can be calculated in real time without resorting to a deep learning model, making it an ideal solution for resource-constrained systems, such as embedded devices or browser-based applications. Detection is performed with minimal computational cost, while maintaining good responsiveness, even on modest platforms.

However, although this approach is effective under normal conditions, it has limitations in complex situations such as partial occlusions, angle variations, or low light conditions. In order to improve the robustness of the system, a validation step using a convolutional neural network has been integrated. This step only occurs when the EAR value is in a zone of uncertainty, or when classification errors are likely, which significantly reduces false positives and false negatives while maintaining real-time execution.

1) *Data set preparation* : To train a CNN model capable of accurately distinguishing between open and closed eyes, a representative and balanced data set was constructed from 1,048 royalty-free videos from the Pexels platform [22]. These videos show individuals blinking in a variety of contexts (angles, lighting, facial expressions). Images (frames) were automatically extracted at a rate of 5 images per second, or one image every 0.2 seconds. This process resulted in a corpus of 84,343 images, ensuring sufficient temporal coverage of the blinking sequences.

Next, a subset of 8,000 images was annotated manually : 4,000 images showing open eyes and 4,000 showing closed eyes. This annotation phase was carried out with care to ensure optimal label quality, which is crucial for supervised learning.

The images were then converted to greyscale to reduce the dimensionality of the data and computational costs without significant loss of information, as the differences between eye states

are based primarily on shape and contrast rather than colour.

Finally, the dataset was organised into a binary structure, with two separate folders : open_eyes_images/ and closed_eyes_images/. This separation made it possible to directly feed Keras image generators for training and validating the CNN model.

This balanced and varied database provides a solid foundation for training a high-performance binary classifier capable of compensating for the limitations of EAR in ambiguous cases.

2) *CNN model architecture (MobileNetV2)*: The validation model is based on MobileNetV2[9], a lightweight convolutional neural network architecture specially designed for resource-constrained environments [2]. This choice is in line with our objective of maintaining real-time execution while improving the system's accuracy in ambiguous cases detected by EAR. MobileNetV2[9] introduces inverted residual blocks and separable depthwise convolutions, which significantly reduce computational complexity while maintaining feature extraction capabilities comparable to those of deeper networks.

In our implementation, the MobileNetV2 [9] model was used as a feature extractor, without its final classification layers. We added a custom head consisting of the following elements :

- A Flatten layer to transform feature maps into vectors ;
- A dense layer of 128 neurons with the ReLU6 activation function, which is particularly well suited to quantised models [3] ;
- A Dropout regularisation layer with a rate of 50% to reduce the risk of overfitting ;
- A single-neuron Dense output layer, activated by a sigmoid function, producing a probability indicating whether the eye is open or closed.

This architecture enables efficient binary classification while limiting the size of the model, which is crucial for integration into embedded or web applications.

3) *Training and regularisation* : The model was trained on a balanced and pre-processed dataset (greyscale images, resolution 224×224 pixels). The model was compiled with the BinaryCrossentropy loss function, standard for

binary classification tasks, and optimised using the Adam algorithm [4], known for its stability and fast convergence.

The following hyperparameters were used :

- Learning rate : 0.001
- Batchsize : 32
- Epochs : 10

To improve the model's generalisation and simulate real- world conditions, data augmentation was applied in real time during training using an image generator (ImageDataGenerator). The transformations used include :

- Random rotations (up to $\pm 10^\circ$) ;
- Horizontal/vertical translations (up to 10%) ;
- Zooms (up to 10%).

The model's performance was evaluated at each epoch on an independent validation set. The final accuracy obtained on this set is approximately 95%, with a loss stabilised around 0.15, demonstrating a good compromise between bias and variance. (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 Training over 10 epochs

The combination of this lightweight architecture and regularisation techniques has resulted in a reliable, fast and generalisable model that is perfectly suited to secondary validation of EAR predictions in difficult conditions.

4) *EAR-CNN integration for pipeline optimisation* : The integration of the two approaches, EAR and CNN (MobileNetV2), is at the heart of our hybrid strategy. This two-step pipeline leverages the complementary strengths of each method, while circumventing their respective weaknesses (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4 : Proposed system

The process is structured as follows :

(1) Initial detection by EAR :

- For each frame, the EAR is calculated from the key points provided by MediaPipe [2].
- If the EAR value is clearly above or below the threshold ($EAR > 0.27$ or $EAR < 0.21$), a decision is made immediately (eyes open or closed).
- If the EAR falls within an ambiguous range (typically $0.21 \leq EAR \leq 0.27$), the frame is sent to the CNN for validation.

(2) Validation by the CNN :

- The MobileNetV2 classifier only intervenes on these "uncertain" frames.
- The image is resized and pre-processed before being submitted to the model.
- The CNN output (sigmoid probability) is interpreted with a threshold of 0.5 to determine the actual state of the eye.

This conditional strategy significantly reduces the computational load, since the majority of frames are processed quickly via EAR alone. Only ambiguous images require the more costly inference of the CNN model. This increases overall robustness without compromising real-time performance.

- A reduction in false positives/negatives, particularly in complex scenarios (occlusions, extreme angles) ;
- Optimised resource consumption, thanks to conditional activation of the CNN ;
- Improved tolerance to environmental variations, making the system more

suitable for embedded or mobile applications ;

In practice, this combination achieves an overall accuracy of 95% while maintaining an average processing time of 19 ms per image, or approximately 50 images per second, which meets the requirements for real-time operation.

III. RESULTS

A. Model evaluation

The proposed system was evaluated using an annotated dataset comprising 8,000 images divided equally between the "eyes open" and "eyes closed" classes. This phase validated the predictive and computational performance of the hybrid solution.

1) *Overall accuracy* : The combined EAR + CNN system achieved an overall accuracy of 95%, demonstrating a good balance between sensitivity and specificity. This result was obtained after 10 training epochs, with performance stabilising on the validation set from the eighth epoch onwards.

2) *Average processing time* : The inference time was measured for two distinct cases :

- EAR method alone : ~9 ms per image, or approximately 111 images/second.
- EAR + CNN pipeline : ~19 ms per image, or a frequency of ~50 images/second.

Fig. 5 Graph showing the execution time for each stage of the pipeline.

These results confirm the system's compatibility with real-time constraints, even when CNN validation is required on certain frames. This selective architecture minimises resource consumption while ensuring the robustness of final decisions.

3) *Confusion matrix* : The confusion matrix compares the actual values of a target variable with those predicted by a model. In short, it allows for a detailed assessment of the quality of the

classification by distinguishing between correct predictions and errors.

The matrix (Fig. 6) is broken down as follows :

- True positives (TP) : the model correctly predicted 8,748 closed eyes.
- False positives (FP) : the model incorrectly classified 700 open eyes as closed. This is a false alarm.
- True negatives (TN) : 8,324 open eyes were correctly detected by the model.
- False negatives (FN) : The model predicted that 299 closed eyes were open.

Fig. 6 Confusion matrix

Ces résultats se traduisent par les taux suivants :

- TP : 48 %,
- TN : 46 %,
- FP : 4 %,
- FN : 2 %

3) *Accuracy and loss curves* : Fig. 7 illustrates the curves showing the evolution of accuracy and the loss function. (Loss) curves during training. We observe a steady increase in accuracy across the training set, reaching 0.95 at the end of the 10th epoch. Loss, on the other hand, decreases continuously to converge around 0.15, both on the training and validation data. The absence of overfitting is confirmed by the proximity between the two curves.

Fig. 7 Learning curves (accuracy and loss) over 10 epochs.

5) *Classification report* : The classification report obtained at the end of the evaluation is presented in Table I. It confirms the balanced performance of the model on both classes.

TABLE I
CLASSIFICATION REPORT FOR THE CNN MODEL

Classe	Accuracy	Recall	F1-Score
Eyes closed	0.95	0.97	0.96
Eyes open	0.95	0.93	0.94
Average	0.95	0.95	0.95

These metrics show that the system is both accurate in its predictions and capable of effectively detecting blinks, even in complex situations.

B. Experimental results

Beyond the traditional metrics, a series of practical tests was carried out to evaluate the system's behaviour in a variety of conditions, reflecting real-life scenarios. These experiments aim to demonstrate the robustness of the hybrid approach (EAR + CNN) in the face of common visual disturbances.

Three situations were specifically studied :

- (1) Standard lighting,
- (2) Low light,
- (3) Partial occlusions, for example when wearing

1) *Standard lighting (Fig.8)* : In a well-lit environment, the system maintained a detection accuracy of 96%, with a very low false positive/negative rate. Facial landmarks were detected consistently and natural variations in the face did not affect the results.

Fig. 8 Eye status under standard lighting conditions

2) *Low light (Fig. 9)* : Under dim or indirect lighting, performance decreased slightly to 91% accuracy. This decrease is mainly due to difficulties in detecting key points by MediaPipe², especially when contrasts are low. Nevertheless, the CNN validation phase corrected several initial errors generated by the EAR.

Fig. 9 Eye condition under low light conditions

3) *Partial occlusions (Fig. 10)* : The system was also tested in situations where the eyes were partially obstructed, such as by thick-rimmed glasses or hands briefly passing in front of the face. In these cases, the observed accuracy was 88%. The CNN module, thanks to its training on diverse images, was able to compensate for several EAR detection failures, but the loss of landmark visibility remains a limiting factor.

Fig. 10 : Eye status under conditions of partial occlusion (glasses)

5) *Qualitative visualisation* : The images captured during the tests show correct detection of open/closed eyes, even in cases of variations in brightness or position. The superimposition of landmarks (key facial points) allows the accuracy of the location to be visually verified.

Fig. 11 Eye landmarks by Mediapipe

These results highlight the system's ability to operate in realistic, uncontrolled environments, making it a strong candidate for embedded applications such as driver assistance, contactless interfaces, and vigilance monitoring.

C. Comparison with existing methods

To evaluate the relevance of our hybrid EAR–CNN approach, we conducted a comparative study with several eye blink detection methods presented in the literature. The analysis focused on three essential criteria : accuracy, execution time, and robustness against environmental disturbances.

1) *Methods compared* : The approaches selected for comparison are as follows :

- Capacitive detection on connected glasses [1]
- HaarCascade + CNN method (Aouadi & Berrahil, 2021) [2]
- Dlib + CNN pipeline deployed on Raspberry Pi (Benaissa & Lardjane, 2023) [3]
- Our hybrid EAR + MobileNetV2 system [23]
- Méthode HaarCascade + CNN (Aouadi & Berrahil,)

2) *Comparative summary (table II)*

TABLE II
COMPARISON OF EXISTING METHODS

Method	Accuracy (%)	Processing time	Robustness in real conditions
Capacitive sensors [1]	92	Real time (but depends on external hardware)	Low (sensitive to movement)
HaarCascade + CNN [2]	99.9	No specified	Average (sensitive to lighting)

Dlib + CNN sur Raspberry Pi [3]	99.4	1,17 à 2,18 sec/image	Average (varies depending on light)
EAR + MobileNetV2 (proposé)	95	19 ms/image	High (even in difficult conditions)

3) *Analysis of results* : Although some methods such as HaarCascade + CNN display very high accuracy, they lack robustness in real-world conditions (changing lighting, partially visible faces) or require specific hardware, such as sensors integrated into glasses.

In addition, some approaches, particularly those deployed on microcontrollers or Raspberry Pi, have processing times that are unsuitable for real-time applications, exceeding 1 second per image. This makes them incompatible with embedded applications that require rapid responses.

Conversely, the system we propose strikes an optimal balance between accuracy, speed and robustness. Thanks to the conditional activation of the CNN, the pipeline remains. Lightweight and responsive while correcting probable errors from the EAR.

4) *Comparative advantages*

- Guaranteed real time (< 20 ms/image on standard machine).
- No external hardware required (standard webcam sufficient).
- Good tolerance to degraded conditions (brightness, occlusions, angles).
- Easily deployable on web browsers or embedded systems.

These elements confirm that the EAR–CNN hybrid architecture is a balanced, reliable and portable solution, well suited to real-time applications on low-resource devices.

IV. DISCUSSION

A. *Performance analysis* : Analysis of the results highlights the relevance of the hybrid approach implemented, both in terms of accuracy and processing speed. The system combines two complementary methods : the geometric approach (EAR), which is fast but sensitive to disturbances, and the MobileNetV2 convolutional neural

network [8], which is more robust but resource-intensive. This combination allows us to take advantage of the benefits of each method, while mitigating their respective limitations. The sequential operation of the pipeline, in which the CNN only intervenes to validate uncertain cases, significantly reduces the number of deep inferences to be performed. In practice, this optimisation has made it possible to maintain an average processing time of 19 ms per image, which is well below the threshold required for real-time applications. In terms of accuracy, the system achieved a stable performance of 95%, both on validation sets and in experimental tests. This consistency is a sign of correct generalisation, partly due to the diversity of the dataset and the use of regularisation techniques (dropout, data augmentation) during model training.

Furthermore, the system has demonstrated its ability to adapt to embedded constraints. Thanks to the compact architecture of MobileNetV2 [9] and conditional processing, the model is lightweight enough to run on resource-constrained platforms, such as microcontrollers or web browsers via TensorFlow [19].js. Unlike heavier models (e.g., VGG, ResNet [7]), our solution does not require a dedicated GPU or server infrastructure, which facilitates its multi-platform deployment.

In summary, the proposed approach achieves an effective compromise between accuracy, speed and portability, making it a viable solution for embedded systems requiring reliable and fast eye blink detection

B. *Limitations*

Although the results obtained are generally satisfactory, certain structural and technical limitations of the system must be acknowledged and analysed.

1) *Dependence on camera quality* : The performance of the pipeline relies heavily on the reliable detection of key facial points by MediaPipe [2]. However, this detection is directly influenced by the quality of the camera used (resolution, refresh rate, ability to handle low light conditions). In our tests, an integrated HD webcam was sufficient to guarantee acceptable

performance, but accuracy drops were observed on some mobile devices with low-quality sensors.

Thus, the system may encounter difficulties in the presence of :

- Motion blur due to a low frame rate;
- Noisy or underexposed images;
- Resolution too low to allow precise eye localisation.

2) *Sensitivity to morphological variability* : Despite the increase in data and the diversity of the training set, the system may be sensitive to morphological variability among individuals. Certain specific profiles, such as deep-set eyes, drooping eyelids, and long eyelashes, can disrupt geometric detection by EAR or negatively influence CNN predictions.

Furthermore, the EAR threshold of 0.24, although effective in most cases, is not customised for each individual. Dynamic or adaptive threshold adjustment could improve inter-individual accuracy, particularly in extreme cases.

3) *Lack of advanced temporal tracking* : The current system operates primarily on a frame-by-frame basis, applying simple threshold rules to consecutive frames to detect blinking. Although sufficient in most cases, this approach does not incorporate advanced temporal logic (such as a Kalman filter, RNN model, or temporal encoder), which could be useful for :

- Distinguishing between voluntary blinking and prolonged fatigue;
- Avoiding micro-false positives related to detection artefacts;
- Modelling eye behaviour over a longer period of time.

In conclusion, these limitations offer clear areas for improvement, without calling into question the viability of the proposed system. They highlight the importance of an adaptive and multimodal approach in future developments.

V. EXPERIMENTAL DEPLOYMENT

A. Objective and challenges

In order to validate the usability of our system in a real-world context, an experimental deployment phase was conducted. The objective

was to offer a solution that is fully accessible via a web browser, without requiring local installation or a heavy server environment. This approach ensures maximum portability, particularly on PCs, tablets and smartphones, while providing multi-platform access (Windows, Android, iOS, etc.).

B. Choice of infrastructure

The deployment was carried out via AWS S3 (Amazon Simple Storage Service), configured in static site hosting mode. This service was chosen for its ease of implementation, high availability and compatibility with serverless architectures. The use of AWS S3 also allows for future integration with complementary services, such as CloudFront (CDN) or Lambda@Edge for advanced optimisations.

C. Model conversion

The model initially trained in Keras format (.h5) was converted to TensorFlow [19].js format using the `tensorflowjs_converter` utility. This conversion generated a set of files consisting of :

- `model.json`: model structure (architecture and topology);
- `group1-shard1of1.bin`: binary weights of the model;

This lightweight version, formatted for the browser, allows inferences to be made directly on the client side, without the need for a remote server, thus ensuring reduced latency, data confidentiality (no image transfer), and processing autonomy.

D. Web application structure

The web application was developed with a simple, modular *architecture* :

- `index.html`: HTML structure of the interface (user interface, video display);
- `script.js`: detection logic (video acquisition, detection via MediaPipe [2], prediction via CNN);
- `modele_js/`: folder containing the converted files (`model.json` and `.bin`).

This structure allows for rapid integration on any host supporting static files, without server or database dependencies.

E. Deployment results

The application was tested on several platforms:

- On PC (Chrome/Firefox browser) (Fig. 12): the interface loaded instantly, the webcam was activated without any compatibility issues, and detection was smooth and continuous. The system maintained a frame rate of 50 FPS, close to local performance.

Fig. 12 PC version deployment test

- On Android smartphone (Fig. 13): the application ran correctly via Chrome mobile. A slight decrease in accuracy was observed, mainly due to the hardware limitations of front cameras (low resolution, latency). However, detection remained functional and usable under standard conditions.

Fig. 13 Mobile version deployment test

F. Conclusion on deployment

This experimental deployment demonstrates the technical feasibility of our system in a standalone web environment, without installation or heavy infrastructure. It paves the way for mobile uses of the system, whether for surveillance, accessibility, or embedded security purposes. The model's portability, lightness, and client-side execution

make it a solution that can be easily integrated into real- world and distributed contexts.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this article, we proposed and evaluated a hybrid approach for real-time eye blink detection, combining the geometric Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) method [1] with a lightweight convolutional neural network based on the MobileNetV2 architecture [9]. The main objective was to meet the constraints of embedded systems and poorly equipped environments, while maintaining a high level of accuracy.

The developed solution achieved an overall accuracy of 95%, with an average processing time of 19 ms/image, confirming its compatibility with real-time requirements. The selective pipeline demonstrated its effectiveness in minimising errors in ambiguous cases, while limiting the computational load. Experimental tests confirmed the robustness of the system, even in varied conditions such as low light or partial occlusions.

Furthermore, the system has been successfully converted and deployed in a web environment, accessible via a browser using TensorFlow [19].js and hosted on AWS S3. This deployment confirms not only the portability of the solution, but also its ability to operate without local installation, paving the way for consumer use on a variety of devices (PCs, smartphones, IoT).

There are numerous potential applications for this system, particularly in the areas of road safety (detection of drowsiness), digital health (passive monitoring of alertness), and accessibility (contactless interfaces for people with reduced mobility).

Looking ahead, integrating the system into embedded platforms such as Jetson Nano or Raspberry Pi, as well as adding advanced time tracking mechanisms, could enhance its analytical capabilities. Furthermore, extending it to related tasks, such as detecting prolonged fatigue or eye tracking, represents a natural evolution of this research towards practical applications in everyday life.

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